

Messalians

also known as “Euchites”

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Christian Traditions, Early Christianity, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Heresy

The Messalians or Euchites was a Christian heresy originated in Mesopotamia around 360-370 CE and existed to about the ninth century. Their teachings spread into Syria and Asia Minor and later to Thrace. The name “Messalian” comes from the Syriac *mšallyānā*, meaning “the person who prays”. The name *euchitēs* comes from the Greek translation of the Oriental name and means the same. The first references to Messalianism appear in the 370's in Ephrem the Syrian's “Contra haereses”, in Epiphanius's “Panarion” and “Ancoratus”, and later in Jerome, Atticus and Sisinnius, Archbishops of Constantinople and Theodotus of Antioch. The term “Messalianism” in fact does not refer to a specific group of people, but it was applied in a pejorative manner to any group of ascetics or monks who seemed to reject the sacramental ordinances of the Church, or who placed an emphasis on empirical aspects of prayer and demonstrated doctrinal and behavioural deviations from orthodox monastic norms. Messalians therefore were ascetics who practiced poverty, celibacy, and fasting, rejected the sacramental life of the Church and claimed that they were able to see God with their physical eyes. Messalianism was first condemned as a heresy at the Synod of Side (Pamphylia) in 388 or 390. They were finally anathematized by the Third Ecumenical Council of Ephesus in 431. Messalianism and Messalian tendencies continued to exist for several centuries, influencing the Bogomils of Bulgaria and, thereby, the Bosnian Church, and Catharism. By the 12th century Messalianism had reached Bohemia and Germany and, by a resolution of the Council of Trier in 1231, was condemned as heretical. Messalians held that the essence of the Holy Trinity could be perceived by the senses. That the Threefold God transformed himself into a single substance to unite with the souls of the perfect and that has taken different forms in order to reveal himself to the senses. Only such sensible revelations of God confer perfection upon the Christian. They also taught that, once someone experienced the essence of God, he was freed from moral obligations or ecclesiastical discipline. They had male and female teachers, the “perfecti”, whom they honored more than the clergy.

Date Range: 360 CE - 900 CE

Region: Mesopotamia, Asia Minor, Syria

Region tags: Middle East, Mesopotamia, Syria, Asia Minor

The expansion of Messalianism, from its origins in Mesopotamia to Syria and Asia Minor.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Liber graduum, ed. Michael Kmosko; *Patrologia Syriaca* 1. 3 (Paris, 1926).

— Source 2: P. Deseille (trans.), *Les Homelies spirituelles de Saint Macaire* (*Spiritualite orientale* 40; Abbaye de Bellefontaine, 1984).

– Source 3: G. Maloney (trans.), *Intoxicated with God: The Fifty Spiritual Homilies of Macarius* (Denville, New Jersey, 1978) [Collection II].

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.arcaneknowledge.org/catholic/councils/comment03.htm>

– Source 1 Description: Commentary on the Council of Ephesus Definition against the Messalians

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://syri.ac/authors-jacob-sarug/book-steps-liber-graduum>

– Source 1 Description: The book of steps: the Syriac "Liber Graduum".

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Lampetius wrote a book called "The Testament", refuted by Severus of Antioch. Another book of Messalians, called The "Asceticus", was condemned at the Third General Ecumenical Council at Ephesus in 431, after it had already been condemned by a Council of Constantinople in 426 and by the local council of Side.

Are they written:

– Yes

Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

Notes: In fact, during the fifth century in Armenia strict decrees were issued against Messalians and they were especially accused of immorality, so that the name "Messalians" in Armenian became the equivalent for "filthy". The Nestorians in Syria did their best to banish Messalianism by legislation.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: On the contrary, an imperial law against heretics, issued in 428(Codex Theodosius XVI, 5,60), explicitly refers to Messalianism and Messalians by name.

Is iconography present:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: In order to avoid persecution, Messalians would deliberately conform to ecclesiastical usages, profess orthodoxy, and deny any heretical doctrines ascribed to them.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Adelphius was their first leader. He was banished with his disciples from Antioch in 376 by the local bishop, Flavian, and was later condemned at the Synod of Side in 388 or 390. Another known leader was Lampetius, their first priest who was ordained in 458 and degraded from his priesthood on account of unpriestly conduct.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: One of their leader, a man named Peter, claimed to be Christ. Before being stoned to death for his blasphemies, he promised his followers that after three days he would rise from his tomb in the shape of a wolf.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Messalians believed that through intense meditation one could achieve union with God and encourage the indwelling of the Holy Spirit, through which sinful

inclinations would be purged and demons would be expelled.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

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Nature of religious group [please select one]:

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↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

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↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Sort of. According to Messalianism, because of Adam’s original sin, every one was born with a demon that incited humans to sin. That, neither baptism nor the Lord’s Supper could expel. The only means for removing the demon was fervent, constant prayer combined with an ascetic lifestyle.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Field doesn't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans’ behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: Messalianism denied that the Sacraments, including baptism, were agents of the Divine Grace and declared that the only spiritual power was constant prayer that led to possession by the Holy Spirit.

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Messalians avoided manual labor and lived mainly from the exploitation of the properties offered by the new members of the sect. To achieve this, they declared themselves against any form of property. At the same time, they appeared to be ruthless and refused charity to those in need, claiming that they were poor in spirit.

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Notes: Messalians held that the Threefold God (the Holy Trinity) transformed himself into a single substance (hypostasis) in order to unite with the souls of the perfect.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

–Yes [specify]: Messalians displayed some kind of hierarchy or some elitism, distinguishing

an order of "perfecti" from the rest. This does not concern a spiritual hierarchy, but it depends on whether the initiate Messalian had received the experience of the "baptism of fire," an emphatically aesthetic experience of the Holy Spirit.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Messalians believed that God has taken different forms in order to reveal himself to the senses.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Messalians considered that the dreams in the state of apathy are prophetic and may reveal the future. This is why they slept for many hours. They regarded dreams as enlightenment of the Holy Spirit.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Messalianism was considered to be an enthusiastic movement, since the sang, danced and rattled during their gatherings. These practices are related to the way they perceived the apparition of the Holy Spirit.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Messalianism taught that because of Adam's original sin every person was born with a

demon. Even Jesus Christ, as they claimed, was born with a demon.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Messalians claimed that they could see the evil spirits that go through the world.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

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Notes: The inherent demons, with which men were born with, were able to incite people to commit sins. Therefore, a certain causal efficacy of these demons in the world was present.

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– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: In a way yes. The Messalians who achieved the desirable state of apathy knew the state of souls after death.

- ↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No

- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

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- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

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that they were poor in spirit.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: However, since the only means for removing the inherent demon was fervent, constant prayer combined with an ascetic lifestyle, the Messalians believed that when someone would achieve a passionless state wherein the demon would escape the body, then sin was impossible. Because the passions of the body no longer ruled, rich food and luxurious living could not stir evil desires in the heart, so the necessity for an ascetic lifestyle was gone.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They were accused nevertheless of orgiastic practices such as incest and homosexuality.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: They generally disregarded discipline in the matter of fasting. Moreover, once they would reach a state of apathy, they would therefore had no inclination towards evil and they could indulge in any kind of abomination.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Once a Messalian would reach a state of apathy, he would therefore had no inclination towards evil and would be free to indulge in any kind of abomination.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Michael Psellos, however, accused them of orgiastic practices such as incest and homosexuality. Furthermore, he argued that children born from such libertine activities were brought before a Satanic assembly after eight days, offered up to Satan and then cannibalistically eaten. This cannibalistic act was supposedly a parody of baptism.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Although Messalians declared themselves against any form of property, they made their living by exploiting the properties offered by the new members.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Messalians believed that participating in the Divine Liturgy was pointless. Hence, they advised the monks to remain in their own house of prayer and pray.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Messalians believed that participating in the Divine Liturgy was pointless. Hence, they advised the monks to remain in their own house of prayer and pray. They were accused, however, that at their gatherings they sang, danced and rattled.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: However, since the only means for removing the inherent demon was fervent, constant prayer combined with an ascetic lifestyle, the Messalians believed that when someone would achieve a passionless state wherein the demon would escape the body, then sin was impossible. Because the passions of the body no longer ruled, rich food and luxurious living could not stir evil desires in the heart, so the necessity for an ascetic lifestyle was gone.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They were accused nevertheless of orgiastic practices such as incest and homosexuality.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: They generally disregarded discipline in the matter of fasting. Moreover, once they would reach a state of apathy, they would therefore had no inclination towards evil and they could indulge in any kind of abomination.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Once a Messalian would reach a state of apathy, he would therefore had no inclination towards evil and would be free to indulge in any kind of abomination.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Michael Psellos, however, accused them of orgiastic practices such as incest and homosexuality. Furthermore, he argued that children born from such libertine activities were brought before a Satanic assembly after eight days, offered up to Satan and then cannibalistically eaten. This cannibalistic act was supposedly a parody of baptism.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Although Messalians declared themselves against any form of property, they made their living by exploiting the properties offered by the new members.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Messalians believed that participating in the Divine Liturgy was pointless. Hence, they advised the monks to remain in their own house of prayer and pray.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Messalians believed that participating in the Divine Liturgy was pointless. Hence, they advised the monks to remain in their own house of prayer and pray. They were accused, however, that at their gatherings they sang, danced and rattled.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: At first Messalianism included only laymen. Gradually however Messalian beliefs and attitudes made their way in ascetic and ecclesiastical communities.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Messalians had no jobs and they lived by begging.

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Both books that Messalian leaders composed, Lampetius's "Testament" and the "Asceticon" were written in Greek language. Other ascetic texts or text corpora related with or influenced by Messalian teachings is the "Book of Steps (Liber Graduum)", written in Syriac (late 4th century CE) and the Pseudo Macarian homilies that were originally written in Greek and then translated into Syriac, Arabic and

Georgian language.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: On the contrary, they denied eleemosynary deeds.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: At first Messalianism included only laymen. Gradually however Messalian beliefs and attitudes made their way in ascetic and ecclesiastical communities.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: On the contrary, they denied eleemosynary deeds.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Both books that Messalian leaders composed, Lampetius's "Testament" and the "Asceticon" were written in Greek language. Other ascetic texts or text corpora related with or influenced by Messalian teachings is the "Book of Steps (Liber Graduum), written in Syriac (late 4th century CE) and the Pseudo Macarian homilies that were originally written in Greek and then translated into Syriac, Arabic and Georgian language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Messalians had no jobs and they lived by begging.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

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